

DETERMINANTS OF ANEMIA IN PROSPECTIVE BRIDES IN THE WORKING AREA OF UPTD PUSKESMAS BATOH, BANDA ACEH

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Abstract

Anemia is one of the most common public health problems worldwide, particularly affecting women of childbearing age (brides-to-be) who will later give birth to future generations. Factors associated with anemia include iron tablet intake, nutritional status, the menstrual cycle, eating habits, and knowledge. The consequences of anemia include an increased risk of chronic energy deficiency (CED), inhibited fetal growth (IFG), premature birth, low birth weight (LBW), and developmental disorders in children. This study aimed to determine the determinants of anemia among prospective brides in the working area of UPTD Puskesmas Batoh, Lueng Bata District, Banda Aceh City. An analytical survey method with a cross-sectional design was used. The sample consisted of 56 brides-to-be, selected through total sampling. Data analysis involved univariate and bivariate analyzes using the Chi-square test. The univariate results showed that, among the 56 respondents, most did not have anemia (63.3%), consumed iron tablets (53.3%), had normal nutritional status (46.7%), regular menstrual cycles (60%), good eating habits (62%), and good knowledge (56.7%). The bivariate analysis revealed significant relationships between anemia and iron tablet consumption ($p = 0.003$), nutritional status ($p = 0.009$), menstrual cycle ($p = 0.001$), eating habits ($p = 0.001$), and knowledge ($p = 0.002$) in prospective brides. The study concluded that there were significant relationships between these factors and anemia.

Keywords: Anemia, Determinants, Brides

1. INTRODUCTION

Future brides and grooms need comprehensive information about reproductive health as they approach their wedding. This information is crucial because there are still many misconceptions about reproductive health [1]. Pre-wedding health preparation is particularly important for women, who, as future mothers, need to ensure their health is optimized to support a healthy pregnancy and to produce a healthy, intelligent baby. Common reproductive health issues among prospective brides include sexually transmitted infections, unintended pregnancies, chronic energy deficiency (CED), and anemia [2].

Anemia is one of the most widespread public health problems globally, especially among women of reproductive age. It is characterized by hemoglobin levels in the blood falling below

normal, typically below 12 g/dL. This condition often results from deficiencies in essential nutrients needed for blood formation, such as iron, folic acid, or vitamin B12 [3].

Many cases of anemia are found in women of reproductive age, a critical stage that is both vulnerable and at high risk for health issues. Factors influencing anemia in this group include income, consumption of iron tablets, nutritional status, menstrual cycle, knowledge, infections, and eating patterns [4].

The impact of anemia on prospective brides includes an increased risk of chronic energy deficiency (CED), complications such as obstructed fetal growth, premature birth, low birth weight (LBW), stunting, neurocognitive disorders, and bleeding during delivery, which can endanger both mother and baby. Babies born to anemic mothers may suffer from low iron levels, continuing to experience anemia in infancy and early childhood, thereby increasing neonatal and infant morbidity and mortality rates [5].

Globally, the prevalence of anemia in women of reproductive age is 30% [6]. According to the Basic Health Research (Riskesdas) in 2018, 48.9% of women of reproductive age were anemic, indicating a significant proportion of prospective brides may suffer from this condition [7]. Anemia poses a danger to both pregnancy and childbirth, but unfortunately, the issue persists as it tends to perpetuate across generations. Data from the Ministry of Health (Kemenkes) in 2021 show that Indonesia had 233,000 prospective brides, but only 84% had received pre-marital counseling, with a target of 100% [8].

Recent research Dahlia [9] has explored the relationship between menstrual cycle, food intake, and nutritional status with anemia among prospective brides and grooms at the Toboali Community Health Center. The study found a connection between menstrual cycle (p value 0.009) and anemia. This is supported by Ardiyanti [10], who found a link between iron sufficiency (p value 0.008) and anemia in prospective brides and grooms, and Hazmi [11] research (identified relationships between iron tablet consumption (p value 0.023), income (p value 0.001), knowledge (p value 0.0034), and nutritional intake (p value 0.001) with anemia in women of reproductive age.

Government efforts to prevent anemia in prospective brides include health promotion activities, increasing iron-rich food consumption, providing iron supplements, and fortifying foods with iron and folic acid. In Aceh Province, data from the Aceh Provincial Health Service for 2022 shows that 55.3% of women of reproductive age experienced anemia. Among 55,680 couples in Aceh Province, only 79% have participated in pre-marital counseling, with a target of 100% [12].

In Banda Aceh City, the prevalence of anemia among prospective brides was 35.9%, with 127 out of 353 candidates affected. The highest prevalence of anemia was reported at the Community Health Center Batoh (31%), followed by Meuraxa (26.7%), Jaya Baru (26.6%), Kuta Alam (24.2%), Baiturrahman (23.8%), Ulee Kareng (22.8%), Kopelma Darussalam (18.7%), Lampaseh (18.1%), and Lampulo (14.2%) [13].

From April to June 2024, 56 prospective brides were examined, and hemoglobin levels revealed that 3 individuals were anemic. Interviews indicated a lack of iron tablet consumption, inadequate nutritional intake, limited knowledge about anemia, and irregular menstrual cycles among these candidates. Based on these observations, the author aims to analyze the determinants of anemia among prospective brides and grooms in the UPTD Puskesmas Work Area Batoh Subdistrict, Lueng Bata, Banda Aceh City.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research utilizes an analytical survey method with a cross-sectional design, conducted in July 2024. The study population includes all prospective brides and grooms in

the UPTD Puskesmas working area of Batoh Subdistrict, Lueng Bata, Banda Aceh City. The sample was taken using total sampling, resulting in a total of 56 prospective brides. The dependent variable in this study is anemia, while the independent variables include Fe tablet consumption, nutritional status, menstrual cycle, eating habits, and knowledge. Data analysis was conducted using univariate and bivariate methods, with the Chi-Square test performed using SPSS software.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Univariate Analysis

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Age, Education and Information for the Bride and Groom

Characteristics Subject	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age		
20-35 years	50	90
>35 years	6	10
Education		
Primary	4	6,7
Secondary	37	66.7
Tertiary	15	26.6
Information		
Yes	56	100
No	0	0

Based on Table 1, it is evident that the majority of the 56 respondents are aged 20-35 years, with 50 respondents (90%) falling into this age group. Regarding education, most respondents (66.7%) have attained a secondary level of education, and all respondents (100%) have received relevant information as prospective brides and grooms.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents Based on Anemia, Fe Tablet Consumption, Nutritional Status, Menstrual Cycle, Eating Habits, and Knowledge of Prospective Brides

Variable	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Anemia		
Anemic	21	36.7
Not Anemic	35	63.3
Consumption of Fe Tablets		
Yes	30	53.3
No	26	46.7
Nutritional Status		
Thin	17	30
Normal	26	46.7
Overweight	13	23.3
Cycle Menstruation		
Regular	34	60
Irregular	22	40
Eating Habits		
Good	35	62
Poor	21	38

Knowledge		
Good	32	56.7
Insufficient	24	43.3
Total	56	100

Based on Table 2, the majority of the 56 respondents did not experience anemia, with 35 respondents (63.3%) falling into this category. Most respondents (53.3%) consumed Fe tablets, 46.7% had normal nutritional status, and 60% had a regular menstrual cycle. Additionally, 62% of respondents had good eating habits, and 56.7% had good knowledge.

3.2 Analysis Bivariate

Table 3. Relationship between Fe Tablet Consumption, Nutritional Status, Menstrual Cycle, Eating Habits, and Knowledge with Anemia in Prospective Brides

Variable	Anemia				Amount		P-Value
	Anemia		Not Anemic		f	%	
	f	%	f	%			
Consumption of Fe Tablets							
Yes	2	6.3	28	93.8	30	100	0.003
No	19	71.4	7	28.6	26	100	
Nutritional status							
Thin	13	77.8	4	22.2	17	100	0.009
Normal	6	21.4	20	78.6	26	100	
Overweight	2	14.3	11	85.7	13	100	
Cycle Menstruation							
Regular	4	11.1	30	88.9	34	100	0.001
Irregular	17	75	5	25	22	100	
Eating Habits							
Good	7	21	28	79	35	100	0.001
Poor	15	72.7	6	27.3	21	100	
Knowledge							
Good	4	11.8	28	88.2	32	100	0.002
Insufficient	17	69.2	7	30.8	24	100	

Based on the results in Table 3, the Chi-Square test analysis shows a significant relationship between Fe tablet consumption and anemia with a p-value of 0.003. Among the 30 respondents who consumed Fe tablets, the majority (28 respondents, 93.8%) did not experience anemia, whereas among the 26 respondents who did not consume Fe tablets, the majority (19 respondents, 71.4%) experienced anemia.

The Chi-Square test results for nutritional status also show a significant relationship with anemia (p-value = 0.009). Among the 26 respondents with normal nutritional status, the majority (20 respondents, 78.6%) did not experience anemia. However, among the 17 respondents with a thin nutritional status, the majority (13 respondents, 77.8%) experienced anemia. Additionally, among the 13 respondents with a fat nutritional status, the majority (11 respondents, 85.7%) did not experience anemia.

The Chi-Square test results for the menstrual cycle indicate a significant relationship with anemia (p-value = 0.001). Among the 34 respondents with a regular menstrual cycle, the majority (30 respondents, 88.9%) did not experience anemia, while among the 22 respondents with an irregular menstrual cycle, the majority (17 respondents, 75%) experienced anemia.

The Chi-Square test results for eating habits reveal a significant relationship with anemia (p-value = 0.001). Among the 35 respondents with good eating habits, the majority (28 respondents, 79%) did not experience anemia. In contrast, among the 21 respondents with poor eating habits, the majority (15 respondents, 72.7%) experienced anemia.

The Chi-Square test results for knowledge show a significant relationship with anemia (p-value = 0.002). Among the 32 respondents with good knowledge, the majority (28 respondents, 88.2%) did not experience anemia, whereas among the 24 respondents with insufficient knowledge, the majority (17 respondents, 69.2%) experienced anemia.

3.3 Connection Between Fe Tablet Consumption and Anemia in Prospective Brides

Prospective brides who do not consume Fe tablets are more likely to suffer from anemia compared to those who do consume them. This is because Fe tablets are essential for preventing anemia. Some prospective brides who take Fe tablets but still suffer from anemia may be consuming them with tea instead of plain water. This is because tea reduces nausea, which some brides experience when taking Fe tablets. However, consuming tea with Fe tablets reduces their effectiveness. The reluctance to consume Fe tablets is often due to side effects such as nausea, headaches, and black stools, leading some brides to avoid taking them altogether.

This finding aligns with Setyobudihono [14] theory, which states that habits like consuming coffee and tea can cause anemia by inhibiting iron absorption due to tannins (catechins and bioflavonoids) present in these beverages. Proper monitoring of iron supplement consumption, including how they are consumed, is crucial for ensuring effective absorption. Research by Paramashanti [15] supports this, showing that coffee and tea can hinder iron absorption.

Observations suggest that low awareness among prospective brides about the importance of taking Fe tablets contributes to anemia. Despite continuous socialization efforts in villages and schools, many brides still neglect to take Fe tablets, influenced by societal mindsets that perceive Fe tablets as unnecessary or bothersome. This mindset, combined with the fear of nausea and reduced appetite after taking Fe tablets, prevents many brides from consuming them.

To achieve a healthy and intelligent generation by 2045, efforts must begin early by preparing a healthy and well-informed population [16]. Low awareness among prospective brides about the importance of Fe tablets is also influenced by their parents and environment. Knowledge about the importance of taking Fe tablets needs to be more widespread, as it is proven effective in reducing anemia and its consequences during pregnancy.

This assumption aligns with Astuti [17] research on the impact of counseling, reproductive health examinations, and administering Fe tablets on the knowledge and awareness of reproductive health among prospective brides as a stunting prevention effort in Cinere District in 2022. The study found a significant influence (p-value = 0.000)

of administering Fe tablets on the knowledge and awareness of reproductive health among prospective brides.

The government's efforts to prevent anemia in adolescent girls include launching the Iron Nutrition Anemia Prevention and Mitigation Program (PPAGB), which aims to reduce the prevalence of iron deficiency anemia. Fe tablets are provided once a day for one month before marriage to prospective brides. The role of health officers in promoting the PPAGB program includes socializing the administration of Fe tablets [7].

Hemoglobin is a crucial protein in the human body responsible for transporting oxygen from the lungs to peripheral tissues and carrying CO₂ from the tissues to the lungs. Hemoglobin deficiency, often caused by a lack of iron in the body, can lead to anemia. Iron is a vital mineral for the formation of hemoglobin and plays a significant role in the body's enzyme systems. For adolescents, iron helps prevent anemia and supports brain cell growth [18]

One of the factors affecting hemoglobin levels in the blood is the intake of nutrients. The production of red blood cells runs smoothly when the necessary nutrients for hemoglobin formation are available. Iron is a key component of hemoglobin, while vitamin C and protein help with iron absorption. emphasizes that iron is essential for forming hemoglobin [19].

This finding is consistent with Hazmi [11] research on the factors associated with anemia in women of reproductive age in Triolek Factory, North Lampung, which found a significant relationship between Fe tablet consumption (p-value = 0.023) and anemia in women of reproductive age.

3.4 Relationship Between Nutritional Status and Anemia in Prospective Brides

Research observations indicate a relationship between nutritional status and anemia, with prospective brides who have inadequate nutrition more likely to suffer from anemia compared to those with sufficient nutrition. This is because inadequate nutrition leads to a deficiency of essential nutrients, increasing the risk of anemia. Some brides with inadequate nutrition do not suffer from anemia, possibly due to other influencing factors, such as not taking Fe tablets or having irregular menstrual cycles.

Nutrition is a crucial component that supports growth and development. Proper nutrition provides essential nutrients like protein, carbohydrates, fats, minerals, vitamins, and water, necessary for growth and development [20]. Nutritional status reflects the balance between the nutrients entering the body and what is needed. This status is determined by a person's long-term nutrient intake, and in the case of prospective brides, it indicates whether their nutrition is sufficient or lacking [4]. This finding is supported by Ardiyani [10] study, which found a significant connection between nutrient adequacy (p-value = 0.008) and anemia in prospective brides.

3.5 Connection Between Menstrual Cycle and Anemia in Prospective Brides

There is a connection between menstrual patterns and anemia in adolescents. Abnormal menstruation, such as heavy or prolonged bleeding, can lead to significant blood loss, resulting in iron deficiency. Menstruation involves the shedding of the uterine lining and occurs regularly, except during pregnancy. Menarche typically occurs between ages 12-13 but can range from 8 to 16 years old. Menstruation marks the beginning of a woman's reproductive life, continuing until menopause [21].

Regular menstruation indicates that the reproductive organs are functioning properly. It typically occurs every 22-35 days, with menstruation lasting 2-7 days [22].

Dahlia [9] research on the connection between the menstrual cycle, food intake, and nutritional status with anemia in prospective brides at the Toboali Community Health Center found a significant relationship between the menstrual cycle (p -value = 0.009) and anemia in prospective brides.

3.6 Connection Between Eating Habits and Anemia in Prospective Brides

This research shows that prospective brides with poor eating habits are more likely to develop anemia. Many brides limit their food intake, consuming only their preferred foods, often relying on ready-to-eat meals without considering their nutritional content. Additionally, some brides do not regularly include vegetables in their diets.

Tanti [23] highlights that eating habits are also influenced by the environment, particularly cultural practices that are difficult to change, such as the habit of consuming ready-to-eat meals. Poor eating habits can result in a lack of essential nutrients.

Some brides also regularly consume tea with their meals, which contains tannins that can inhibit iron absorption by binding to iron [14]. Brides who do not experience anemia tend to have good eating habits, consuming foods rich in protein and vitamin C, such as a variety of side dishes and fruits. Akib [24] research similarly concludes that non-anemic adolescent girls often consume animal protein and choose fruit as a source of vitamin C, preferring to prepare their food and select nutritious snacks.

3.7 Connection Between Knowledge and Anemia in Prospective Brides

The research suggests that prospective brides with insufficient knowledge about anemia are more likely to suffer from it. This is because they do not fully understand the causes and prevention of anemia, such as the importance of consuming iron-rich foods and Fe tablets. Many brides are unaware that not consuming iron-rich foods and Fe tablets can lead to anemia.

Anemia can also result from a lack of knowledge about proper food preparation methods, which can destroy or reduce the nutrients in food [25]. Nutritional knowledge, particularly about iron, is essential for women of reproductive age when planning their diets. Without this knowledge, it is difficult to create a balanced diet. Foods that increase iron levels include protein sources like meat, fish, eggs, and green vegetables like spinach [26].

This finding is consistent with Hazmi [11] research on factors associated with anemia in women of reproductive age in Triolek Factory, North Lampung, which found a significant connection between knowledge (p -value = 0.0034) and anemia in women of reproductive age.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study, conducted among 56 respondents in the UPTD Puskesmas Batoh, Banda Aceh, found significant connections between Fe tablet consumption (p -value = 0.003), nutritional status (p -value = 0.009), menstrual cycle (p -value = 0.001), eating habits (p -value = 0.001), and knowledge (p -value = 0.002) with anemia in prospective brides. Therefore, it is crucial to promote and provide counseling on these factors, particularly for prospective brides of reproductive age, to improve health awareness and encourage early health check-ups.

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